

APPLICATION OF MIXTURE LAW TO RHEOCHOR. PART IV

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Mixture law has been found to be applicable for non-associated liquids in associated solvents over the entire range of molar fraction and at temperatures examined *i.e.*, 30°, 40° and 50°. The mixtures studied are toluene, benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride in acetic acid, and toluene in acetone.

The application of mixture law to rheochor has been extended in this paper to liquid mixtures containing associated liquids in non-associated liquids. To study the applicability, the molar fraction has been varied over the whole range from 0 to 1 and because the value of rheochor varies with temperature the investigations have been carried out at different temperatures also. The following tables give our results.

α , D , M_m , R_m and R_r have the same significance as given in previous papers (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 533; 1948, 25, 165, 575 *et seq.*)

Non-associated Liquids in Associated Solvents

TABLE I

Toluene in acetic acid.

R (acetic acid, exptl.) = 77.6.

Temp. 10°.

α .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_r .
0.0642	1.015	9.568	62.10	81.17	133.7
0.2052	0.9625	7.538	66.61	89.00	133.2
0.7929	0.8676	5.530	85.47	122.00	133.6

Realc. for toluene = 132.0. $R_{obs.} = 133.$

Temp. = 40°.

0.0642	1.0050	9.448	62.10	81.12	132.2
0.5052	0.9625	6.513	66.61	88.91	132.8
0.7929	0.8511	4.859	85.47	122.10	133.6

$R_{obs.} = 133.0.$

Temp. = 50°.

0.0642	0.9933	8.722	52.10	81.21	133.3
0.4800	0.8855	4.846	75.44	103.80	132.4
0.7929	0.8499	4.171	85.47	122.10	133.6

$R_{obs.} = 133.0.$

TABLE II

Benzene in acetic acid.

Temp. = 30°.					
x .	D.	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m	R_x .
0.1603	0.9933	8.519	62.94	82.83	110.4
0.3900	0.9430	6.887	67.08	90.55	110.8
0.7224	0.8964	5.822	73.06	101.50	110.9
Re _{calc.} for benzene = 109.8. Re _{obs.} = 110.6.					
Temp. = 40°.					
0.1603	0.9822	7.841	62.94	82.90	110.6
0.3900	0.9340	6.245	67.08	90.50	110.7
0.7224	0.8876	5.111	73.06	100.90	109.8
Re _{obs.} = 110.4.					
Temp. = 50°.					
0.1603	0.9716	7.112	62.94	82.80	109.0
0.3900	0.9210	5.776	67.08	99.60	110.69
0.7224	0.8798	4.939	76.06	101.40	110.6
Re _{obs.} = 110.0					

TABLE III

Chloroform in acetic acid.

Temp. = 30°.					
x .	D.	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0819	1.074	8.986	64.00	79.49	100.4
0.2500	1.151	7.244	74.90	83.38	100.7
0.7464	1.357	5.285	104.30	94.66	100.8
Re _{calc.} for chloroform = 100.2. Re _{obs.} = 100.6.					
Temp. = 40°.					
0.0819	1.064	8.287	64.90	79.45	100.2
0.2500	1.1751	6.532	74.90	83.43	100.9
0.7464	1.347	4.840	104.30	94.30	100.3
Re _{obs.} = 100.5.					
Temp. = 50°.					
0.0819	1.051	7.516	64.90	79.47	100.4
0.2500	1.124	5.982	74.90	83.33	100.8
0.7464	1.334	4.537	104.30	94.44	100.5
Re _{obs.} = 100.4					

TABLE IV

Carbon tetrachloride in acetic acid.

<i>x.</i>	<i>D.</i>	Temp. = 30°.			
		$\eta \times 10^3$.	<i>M_m</i> .	<i>R_m</i> .	<i>R_x</i> .
0.0697	1.110	10.71	66.59	80.70	122.0
0.2172	1.228	9.95	80.36	87.18	122.0
0.7482	1.533	8.94	130.20	111.60	122.8
Reals. for CCl ₄ = 122.0. <i>R_{obs.}</i> = 122.0:					
Temp. = 40°.					
0.0697	1.097	9.82	66.59	80.74	122.5
0.2172	1.216	8.76	80.36	87.12	121.7
0.7482	1.517	7.91	130.20	111.20	122.3
<i>R_{obs.}</i> = 122.1					
Temp. = 50°.					
0.0697	1.088	9.17	66.69	80.70	122.0
0.2172	1.196	8.04	80.36	87.14	122.1
0.7482	1.469	6.97	130.20	110.90	121.9
<i>R_{obs.}</i> = 122.1.					

TABLE V

*Toluene in acetone**R* (Acetone, exptl.) = 85.0

<i>x.</i>	<i>D.</i>	Temp. = 30°.			
		$\eta \times 10^3$.	<i>M_m</i> .	<i>R_m</i> .	<i>R_x</i> .
0.0929	0.7938	3.192	61.21	89.16	133.2
0.3674	0.8228	4.169	70.54	102.70	133.2
0.8102	0.8445	4.984	85.65	124.00	133.2
Reals. for toluene = 132.2. <i>R_{obs.}</i> = 133.1					
Temp. = 40°.					
0.0929	0.7825	2.858	61.21	89.20	133.7
0.3674	0.8132	3.952	70.54	103.00	133.2
0.8102	0.8339	4.622	85.65	124.00	133.6
<i>R_{obs.}</i> = 133.5					
Temp. = 50°.					
0.0929	0.7714	2.564	61.21	89.26	133.2
0.3674	0.8021	3.538	70.54	103.00	133.2
0.8102	0.8241	4.467	85.65	124.80	133.1
<i>R_{obs.}</i> = 133.2					

DISCUSSION

The rheochor values for toluene in acetic acid is more or less constant over the whole range of molar concentration and also at the three temperatures 30°, 40° and 50°. The calculated value r_{32} is not very different from the observed value r_{33} (approx.). It appears therefore that the rheochor of toluene does not vary appreciably with temperature, and hence the calculated value which corresponds to boiling point is not very different from the values at lower temperatures.

Rheochor of benzene at different temperatures, as given by Friend and Hargreaves (*Phil. Mag.*, 1943., vii, 34, 644), is as follows :

Temp.	...	60°	80°	100°	140°	180°
R	...	110.4	110.4	109.8	109.8 ¹	109.2

These results show that R varies only slightly with temperature. R_x observed by us in solution therefore at different temperatures is practically the same and not very different from the value at the boiling point (110.4). Our observed value is near about 110. It is further observed that the value is constant over the whole range of molar concentrations studied.

The results with chloroform in acetic acid and toluene in acetone are very similar.

Rheochor of CCl_4 at different temperatures, as given by Friend and Hargreaves (*loc. cit.*), is given below.

Temp.	...	60°	80°	100°	40°	180°
R	...	126.0	125.3	125.1	125.2	124.2

The calculated value from atomic rheochor is 122. The value we obtained is nearer about the calculated value than the value of R , given by Friend and Hargreaves (*loc. cit.*). In general therefore, we conclude that mixture law is applicable for liquid mixtures of associated and non-associated liquids over the whole range of molar concentration and at all temperatures investigated by us.